

PREVALENCE OF PIRIFORMIS SYNDROME AND ITS IMPACT ON QUALITY OF LIFE AMONG FEMALES OF FAISALABAD ISLAMIC EDUCATIONAL CENTERS

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Abstract

Objective: To determine the prevalence of piriformis syndrome and its impact on quality of life among females of Faisalabad Islamic Educational Centers due to long hours sitting.

Methodology: This cross-sectional study was carried out among females of Rahimiya Tahfizul Quran Taqwa Masjid, Albanat Ameniya Rizwiya and Jamia Tul Habib Faisalabad with approval from ethical institutional review board against ref no. TUF/IRB/403/24. A sample size of 130 participants were selected through purposive sampling after informed consent. Female's students aged 10-25 years, sitting on a hard surface for at least one year minimum of 6 hour per day were included in this study. Those with back injury, surgery of back, hip and spine from last 6-months, pre-existing neurological condition (e.g., tremors) and musculoskeletal condition (e.g., fractures), pregnant females were excluded from the study. For diagnosing piriformis syndrome, the Fair test was used, and quality of life was assessed by short form 36. SPSS 20 version was used to analyze the variables.

Results: Piriformis syndrome was present in 25.4% participants. Mean (S.D) of general health, Limitation of activities, Emotional Health problems, social activities pain and energy and emotion was 50.16 (16.71), 66.73 (25.83), 68.65 (23.97), 58.31(24.81), 65.52(22.04), and 57.27 (13.32) respectively.

Conclusion: The analysis of piriformis syndrome among female students in Islamic educational centers reveals a remarkably high incidence rate, accompanied by a predominance of moderate pain intensity among those affected, which significantly affects their quality of life.

INTRODUCTION

Piriformis muscle is a small, flat and pyramidal muscle in the gluteal region, originating from the sacrum and inserting on the femoral trochanter, facilitating external rotation, abduction and hip flexion (1, 2). Piriformis muscle tightness (PMT) can contribute to various problems including low back

pain, sacral dysfunction, sacroilitis, piriformis syndrome and others. This condition occurs when piriformis muscles compress the sciatic nerve. Tightness in the piriformis muscle is a common contributor to piriformis syndrome, as it can put pressure on sciatic nerve that's why symptoms

resembles with sciatica and can affect people of any age, gender and occupation (3, 4). Overuse of piriformis muscle, prolonged sitting, trauma and intense massage can cause piriformis syndrome (5). Patients with the history of severe fall on buttock, extended carpet sitting and prolonged sitting hour on a hard surface are at greater risk for the development of piriformis syndrome (6). Most common complaints of patient is pain, numbness and tenderness in buttock or leg unilateral or sometimes bilateral (7, 8). Patient with Piriformis syndrome can have imbalance issues in their posture when compared to controls and poor quality of life (8, 9). Piriformis muscle stays active in all sitting positions, whether high sitting or cross-legged sitting, although function of piriformis muscle changes with different type of sitting, earlier studies indicates that sitting for more than 8 hours can lead to tightness in the back muscles and strain on the joints (10, 11). It affects women 3 more times than men (12, 13). Treatments include interventions like therapeutic ultrasound, hot and cold compresses, massage and stretching exercises, medications like NSAIDs and muscle relaxants and Botox injections may be an effective treatment for Piriformis Syndrome (14, 15). The hip flexion, adduction and internal rotation (FAIR) test, combined with injections and physical therapy or surgery, seems to be an effective method for diagnosing and treating piriformis syndrome (16, 17).

This study aims to determine the prevalence of piriformis syndrome and its impact on the quality of life among females at an Islamic Educational Centers in Faisalabad, where prolonged sitting is common. The outcome of this study will be helpful in giving awareness about proper biomechanics, posture and the risks associated with prolonged sitting on hard surfaces. The findings can assist healthcare professionals in developing awareness programs focused on ergonomic guidance to prevent piriformis syndrome. Such programs would help reduce the incidence of piriformis syndrome and associated functional disabilities among these individuals.

Methodology

This cross-sectional study was conducted from August 2024 to December 2024 with approval from the ethical institutional review board ref no. TUF/IRB/403/24 at Islamic Educational centers of Rahimiya Tahfizul Quran Taqawa Masjid, Albanat Ameniya Rizwiya, Jamia tul Habib Faisalabad, Pakistan. A purposive sampling technique was employed to recruit a sample of 130 participants. The sample size was calculated using the Raosoft calculator, based on a population size of previous researches i.e.; 195, with a 5% margin of error, a 95% confidence level, and an assumed 50% response distribution. Participants were included in the study based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Female's students aged 10-25 years, sitting on a hard surface for at least one year, sitting a minimum of six hours per day were included in this study. Participants with back injury from last 6 months, surgery of back, hip and spine from last 6 months, pre-existing neurological conditions (e.g., tremors) and musculoskeletal conditions (e.g., fractures), pregnant females were excluded from the study. Fair test was used to diagnose piriformis syndrome which is a reliable diagnostic tool with 0.88 sensitivity and 0.83 specificity rate (18). The patient was positioned in a side lying posture on their unaffected leg during the test. This assessment involved flexion, adduction, and internal rotation of the affected leg for accurately identifying the condition and quality of life was assessed by Short Form 36. Raw score of each domain (General health, limitation of activities, emotional health problems, social activities, pain, and energy and emotions) in the Short Form 36 questionnaire was calculated by computing the mean and SD of each item in the domain. Next, we transformed these raw scores into a standardized 0-100 scale, where 0 indicated the worst possible health state and 100 represented the optimal health state. Finally, we computed the domain scores by averaging the transformed scores for each respective domain. We analyzed the results using SPSS version 20 and described them with the help of frequency and tables, whereas for continuous data, we calculated means \pm SD.

Results:
Data was analyzed and participants have mean age of 16.01 years (SD = 2.53). The study found 74.6% of

participants tested negative and 25.4% tested positive for the FAIR test (Table 1).

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics of Age and Fair Test:

Variable	Constructs	
Age	Minimum	11 years
	Maximum	23 years
	Mean (SD)	16.01 (2.53)
Fair test Impression	Negative (%)	74.6%
	Positive (%)	25.4%

SF-36 survey results reveal varying levels of perceived health and well-being across different dimensions. The highest mean score was seen in the "Social Activities: Emotional Problems" category, indicating fewer limitations due to emotional problems. "Pain" has a relatively high mean score, suggesting moderate pain levels. "Limitation of activities" and "Social activities: the past 4 weeks" also show moderate scores, reflecting some restrictions in daily activities. General health was perceived moderately, indicating

an average health status. However, "physical health problems" and "emotional health problems" have higher variability, suggesting a diverse range of experiences with physical and emotional health issues. Lastly, "energy and emotions" has lower mean scores indicating moderate levels of energy and emotional well-being. Overall, the data shows a mix of moderate health perceptions with significant variability in physical and emotional health problems (Table2).

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics of SF 36

SF-36 VARIABLES	Mean ±SD
Social Activities: Emotional problems	68.65±23.97
Social activities: The past 4 weeks	58.31 ± 24.81
General health	50.16 ± 16.71
Limitation of activities	66.73 ± 25.83
Physical health problem	56.73 ± 37.19
Emotional health problem	59.74 ± 37.97
Pain	65.52 ± 22.04
Energy and emotions	57.27 ± 13.32

Discussion:

The current study's findings indicate that piriformis syndrome has a significant impact on the quality of life of female students, affecting 25.4% of the population. This is consistent with another study that also reported a negative impact of piriformis syndrome on daily living quality(19).

Research findings from 2019 revealed that a significant proportion of participants (65.5%) showed evidence of piriformis tightness among bankers Interestingly, a separate study found that piriformis syndrome affected a quarter of female students (25.4%), resulting in a substantial impact on their quality of life (20).

Another study found a 6.25% prevalence of piriformis syndrome (male: female ratio 1:6.4). In contrast, piriformis syndrome affected 25.4% of female students, significantly impacting quality of life, and 36.9% prevalence of piriformis syndrome in female physical therapy students, linked to prolonged sitting (21).

Current study yielded a notably high prevalence of piriformis syndrome among female students at Islamic Educational Centers in Faisalabad, with a staggering 25.4% of participants affected. In contrast, a significantly lower prevalence of piriformis syndrome was observed among participants with chronic low back pain, affecting 17.2% of this

subgroup. These findings underscore the significance of piriformis syndrome as a distinct clinical entity, particularly among young female populations (22). Another study investigating the prevalence of piriformis syndrome reported a remarkably high incidence of 86.36% among women with low back pain, irrespective of their occupational status. Notably, 80% of working women and 93% of non-working women in the study sample were affected, with no statistically significant difference observed between the two groups. In contrast, our current study revealed a substantial prevalence of piriformis syndrome among female students at Islamic Educational Centers in Faisalabad, affecting 25.4% of participants and significantly impacting their quality of life (11).

Conclusion:

The prevalence of piriformis syndrome among female students at Islamic Educational Centers in Faisalabad was found to be notably high, with affected individuals typically experiencing moderate levels of pain, leading to significant detrimental impacts on their quality of life.

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Ethical Permission: This study was conducted with the approval of EIRB with reference no. TUF/IRB/403/24. And written consent was taken from participants before inclusion in the study.

Conflict of interest: None declared

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